

A Study on Employee Perceptive on 360° Feedback

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Siddiqua, Ayesha, and MP Saravanan. “A Study on Employee Perceptive on 360° Feedback.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 1–10.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575269>

Abstract

360° feedback is a modern method of employee performance evaluation. 360° feedback is the process of gathering confidential and anonymous feedback on an employee’s performance. This feedback comes from their peers, team leaders, mentors, subordinates, or even external stakeholders, such as customers and suppliers. The world of management is progressively getting aware of the fact that seeking and giving employees feedback regularly is necessary to increase employee engagement. Studies have also shown that organizations that adopt 360° assessment have a higher rate of employee engagement and enhance the performance review process. It establishes not only 360° feedback helps employees in their career development but also improves organizational performance. The purpose of the study is to know employee perspectives on 360° feedback. The study has used both primary and secondary data collection. The primary data was collected through random sampling from 50 employees through the questionnaire, and the secondary data was collected through the sources of the internet and magazines. The results indicated that there had been an overall positive impact reported of 360° feedback in one’s professional life.

Keywords: 360° Feedback, Employee Perspective, Employee Evaluation, Employee Performance.

Introduction

While companies are integrating a technique called 360° feedback into their review process. It is a powerful tool for people to improve their performance, particularly at the higher levels in an organization. Companies have found that feedback from employees and customers is helping them avoid any negative impact on organizations. 360° feedback gives employees a balanced perspective on their performance. It helps them gain a thorough knowledge of their performance and allows them to improve themselves. But honest and reliable feedback is necessary to know a person’s perceptions and recognize their previous unseen strengths. It’s incredibly useful for performance management and improvement.

There are times where an organization’s supervisors are biased towards their employees, not always, but occasionally. An employee may feel that he is graded low than he deserved, probably because the supervisor or the manager may not like him for some professional or personal reasons. In context, it is better if the rating is done by all

the members rather than just the supervisor. To control such problems, we use 360° feedback in all organizations.

360° feedback is the procedure through which feedback is collected from several sources apart from the manager, to survey the effectiveness of an employee and develop the overall productivity and the managerial efficiency of an organization. 360° feedback is also known as multi-rater feedback or multi-source feedback. The point is to get a comprehensive perspective on employee performance from conventional sources.

Objectives

1. To know the impact of 360° feedback on employee perspective.
2. To know how it improves employee satisfaction.
3. To know the benefits of 360° feedback.

Literature Review

- **Zand et al. (2017)** exhibited that there are essential contrasts among the methods for 360° as self-appraisals, bosses’ evaluation, partners’ appraisal, and representatives’ evaluation. Then again, there are imperative contrasts among the assessments of chiefs, representatives, and employment stretch while there is no noteworthy distinction between the appraisal done on the premise of 360° criticism show, self-evaluation, the partners’ and administrators’ evaluations and occupation push.
- **Mariam Baloch and Faiza (2016)** carried out a study to analyze the impact of 360° feedback concerning management skills and development. The authors concluded that there is a relationship between assessment and managers develop and between subordinates’ and managers’ development. This feedback also helps the managers to increase their skills and competencies.
- **Samaduzzaman (2014)** discussed that 360° feedback is an effective performance evaluation method to measure the efficiency of a person. The feedback helps in removing the misconceptions or wrong perceptions. The author failed to focus on types of organizations where 360° feedback has been used and has made an impact.
- **Meenakshi.G (2012)** said that 360° feedback appraisal is implemented in most of the organizations for employee appraisal and employee development in organizations. The author concluded that the multifactorial evaluation model is highly crucial in assisting top-level management in analyzing their employees and in making necessary changes in the system. Whenever it is required and 360° feedback is also used to determine the relationship between strategic plan and performance expectation.
- **Manning, T. & Robertson.B (2010)** highlighted the impact of gender differences on seniority level by using 360° assessments which have a behavioral effect on influencing leadership qualities and team behaviors. The author suggested that in every organization, the employees should be familiar with the factors of the changing process and also with the hierarchical systems of authority. The study also imparted on the development of leadership systems in an organization to make well conversant with the changes in different levels of positions both from the aspect of male and female, which ultimately lead to growth in organizational performance.
- **Drew (2009)** highlighted the individual leadership development using 360° feedback. The author analyzed that 360° feedback has a favorable influence in different universities in the aspect of leadership. Here “People engagement” was thoroughly checked by implementing well-defined feedback. 360° feedback is considered as adding value to individuals wherein individuals look into themselves and work on it for their development, thereby meeting the organization’s objective.

- **Mason and Parker-Swift (2009)** highlighted the 360° appraisal, which is a simple, pragmatic solution for doctors. Anonymity is one of the essential factors in a 360° evaluation, which has to be maintained. Here the study revealed that a 360° appraisal is a useful tool for doctors and patients with productive quality service by bringing information regarding revalidation, reassurance, and helpful appraisal.
- **Rao.T.V and Nandini Chawla (2008)** conducted a study on the impact of 360° feedback in four organizations. The research shows that there is a positive impact of 360° feedback in professional life as well as the personal experience of the employees. The author identified specific changes among the employees after 360° feedback viz, communication with the team, self-development, better understanding, etc.
- **Newbold (2008)** says 360° appraisals are classics. 360° estimates a powerful addition to the performance management system. It should be in alignment with the aims of the organization. The author also focused on the success of 360° feedback. It is a success only because of a few factors like the purpose of being apparent, employee preparation, the way it has to be run, and finally, valid delivery of the feedback.
- **Stark, Kornstein&Karani (2008)** highlighted the degree of effect 360° feedback has on the comfort level of faculty and their skills. The study shows that 360° feedback provides the best results when it is used for training purposes. The limitation of the study was that they were not able to figure out the differences in attitudes.

Research Methodology

Statistical Tool

1. Sample Size: The total sample size is 50 employees.
2. Sampling Type: The sampling used for the study was a convenient sampling method.
3. Sampling Unit: The sampling unit is only the employees of different organization
4. Questionnaire: The questionnaire consisting of 11 questions was framed. The survey aimed at knowing the perception and expectations of the employees undergoing this process.

Data Collection

1. Primary Data: The employees of different organizations filled the questionnaire.
2. Secondary Data: Secondary data were collected from newspapers, magazines, journals, online resources, etc.

Overview

360° Feedback

360° feedback is a system and a procedure that allows every employee to get their performance feedback from his/her supervisor or manager and peers, direct reporters, colleagues, and even customers. 360° feedback allows each individual to understand how others view his effectiveness as an employee, coworker, or staff member. The most productive 360° feedback processes provide feedback that is based on behaviors that other employees see.

Benefits of 360° Feedback

1. **Improves self-awareness:** It is the most important benefit of 360° feedback. The reviews provided by the input highlight the areas in which they can improve. Self-awareness refers to understanding your personality, including your strengths, weaknesses, threats, opportunities, beliefs, motivations, thoughts, and emotions.

2. **Increases Accountability:** One remarkable benefit of 360° feedback is that it increases accountability. When you know that several reviewers will be providing you with regular feedback, you automatically become accountable for your actions. An increase in employee accountability has shown to increase their desire to take the initiative and come up with creative methods to improve their performance.
3. **Team Development:** This feedback approach helps team members learn to work more effectively together. Teams know more about their team members’ performance than their supervisors. 360° feedback makes team members more accountable to each other as they share the information that will provide input on each member’s performance. A well-planned procedure can improve communication and team development.
4. **Career Development:** 360° feedback provides employees with an informative assessment of what they need to do in their careers. With the 360° feedback process, an employee is equipped with multiple opportunities to know what they are good at and what needs to be improved.
5. **Provides a Broader Scope for Personal Development:** Feedback received from the perspective of superiors is quite different from that of team members’ or even customers. The employee gets a different view from all peers, managers, customers, and direct reporters against his assessment and thus receives a much better idea of the areas he needs to improve.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table no. 1 Table and Chart Showing the Number of Male and Female Respondents

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	25	50%
Female	25	50%
Total	50	100%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyze that out of 50 respondents, 50% are male, and 50% are female. The table shows that both men and women were keen on giving their opinion on employee perspective towards 360° feedback.

Interpretation

From the above chart, we can interpret that both male and female respondents have given equal responses. In today’s world, both men and women are working hand to hand; this shows that both agree about the concept of 360° feedback.

Table no. 2 Table and Chart Showing the Number of Respondents by Age Group

Age Group	Number of Respondents	Percentage
18-24	25	50%
25-34	12	24%
35-44	11	22%
45-54	2	4%
Above 55	-	-
Total Number of Respondents	50	100%

Analysis

From the above table, we can state that 50% of the respondents are of 18-24 age group, 24% of the respondents belong to 25-44 age group, 22% of the respondents belong to 35-44 age group, 4% of the respondents belong to 45-54 age group and none of the respondents belongs to above 55 age group.

Interpretation

From the above chart, we can interpret that the majority of respondents are youths of the age group 18-24 with 50% as they tend to opt job at a young age. Respondents in the age group of 25-34 are second with 24%, which is less compared to the above age group, the age group of 35-44 are third with 22%, which less than 25-34 age group and the age group of 45-55 are fourth with 4%. In contrast, the age group of 55 above has responded less when compared to other age groups.

Table no. 3 Table and Chart Showing the Level of Experience of Respondents

Level of Experience	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1-2 Years	20	40%
3-4 Years	19	38%
Above 5 Years	11	22%
Total Number of Respondents	50	100%

Analysis

From the above table, we can see out of 50 respondents 40% of them have 1-2 years of experience as they are younger compared to other respondents, 22% of respondents have 3-4 years of experience, and 38% of respondents have above five years of experience as they are senior to other respondents.

Interpretation

From the above chart, we can interpret that 40% of the respondents have less experience compared to other respondents as they are of the age group of 18-24. They are younger than other respondents, and 22% of respondents have more experience than them. Whereas 38% of the respondents have more experience than all other respondents.

Table no. 4 Table and Chart Showing the Qualifications of Respondents

Qualifications	Number of Respondents	Percentage
PG	33	66%
M.Phil.	9	18%
PhD	8	16%
Total Number of Respondents	50	100%

Analysis

From the above table, we can understand that out of 50 respondents; there are 66% PG respondents, 18% are M.Phil. and 16% are Ph.D. respondents. This clearly shows that PG respondents were keener to give their opinion about 360° feedback.

Interpretation

From the above chart, we can interpret that there are more PG respondents when compared to other qualification respondents. This shows that PG respondents are employed more than other respondents.

Table no. 5

Table and Chart Showing Respondents Perspective towards 360° Feedback

According To You, Will 360° Feedback -	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagrees	Strongly Disagrees
Increase Self-Awareness of An Individual	18	31			1
Reduces Negative Behavior	13	32		4	1
Improves Work Relationship	11	35		3	1
Encourages Personal Development	18	29			3
Enhance Performance	20	28		1	1
Revives Work Culture From Within	14	31		4	1
Promotes Progressive Growth	17	29		3	1
Empower Employees	16	25		8	1
Improves Decision Making	20	28		1	1
Improves Employee Satisfaction	17	27		5	1
Boosts Confidence	20	22		7	1
Total Number of Respondents	50				
Percentage	100%				

Analysis

- (i) From the above table, we see that out of 50 respondents, 18 respondents strongly agree with the fact about 360° feedback increase self-awareness of an individual, 31 respondents agree, 0 neutral and disagree, and one respondent strongly disagrees with the event.
- (ii) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 13 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback reduces harmful behavior, 32 agree, 0 neutral, four disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.
- (iii) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 11 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback improves work relationships in organizations, 35 agree, 0 neutral, three disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.
- (iv) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 18 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback reduces harmful behavior, 29 agree, 0 neutral, and disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.
- (v) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 20 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback enhances performance, 28 agree, 0 neutral, one disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.
- (vi) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 14 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback revives work culture from within, 31 agree, 0 neutral, four disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.

- (vii) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 17 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback promotes progressive growth, 29 agree, 0 neutral, three disagrees, and one strongly opposes.
- (viii) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 16 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback empowers employees, 25 agree, 0 neutral, 8 disagrees, and one strongly opposes.
- (ix) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 20 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback improves decision making, 28 agree, 0 neutral, one disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.
- (x) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 17 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback improves employee satisfaction, 27 agree, 0 neutral, five disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.
- (xi) From the above table, we can see that out of 50 respondents, 20 strongly agree with the fact that 360° feedback boosts confidence, 22 agree, 0 neutral, seven disagrees, and one strongly disagrees.

Interpretation

From the above chart, we can interpret that out of 50 respondents, 18 respondents strongly agree with all the above facts, 31 respondents agree, 0 neutral and disagrees, and one respondent strongly disagrees. This shows that 360° feedback has a positive impact on employee perspective. It even proves that 360° feedback helps the overall development of employees as a person.

Findings

1. The study shows that 90% of respondents agree to the fact, about 360° being positive, and 10% disagree.
2. When 360° feedback is implemented efficiently, it provides honest and reliable feedback with complete knowledge that is necessary for employee development.
3. When an employee shows improvement and excels in his job, this will have an impact on the company’s effectiveness and success.
4. It helps in building a strong relationship with team members.
5. Employees are motivated, and they work better because they perceive themselves as others see them.

Suggestions

1. 360° must be implemented effectively in all organizations.
2. The individual employees must be encouraged to take feedback from their superiors and peers regularly. It will ensure a comprehensive Performance Management System.
3. The 360 Degree Feedback System should be free from all kinds of personal biases.
4. The feedback should be provided genuinely. Fair ratings will lead to unbiased results, and this will help in improving the morale of good performers and motivate others to give their best.
5. The areas of improvement can be worked out by developing Training programs following the needs of employees as well as the organization.

Conclusion

Providing feedback for the growth of an employee is useful for all of them because it will help them understand their strengths and weaknesses and how to improve in their careers. 360° feedback procedure is one of the methods for gathering and providing this information. 360° feedback offers progressive growth for both superiors and subordinates to give and receive accurate feedback, which in turn enhances the superior-subordinate relationship. Always try to make the procedure of 360° feedback into the vital culture of the organization. It will give fair reviews and will be more effective. The study also proved that 360° feedback has a positive impact on employee perspective. The employees get all the information they require to improve in their careers. 360° feedback offers potential growth to both employees and the organization in achieving their individual and overall goals.

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